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Foreign Experiences of Regional Industry Transformation and their Application in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *This article explores the transformative experiences of regional industries in various countries and their applicability to Uzbekistan's economic landscape. Additionally, the article discusses potential challenges and opportunities associated with implementing these foreign experiences, providing a framework for policymakers and industry leaders to foster sustainable growth and modernization in Uzbekistan's industrial sector.*

Key words: *gross domestic product, categorized countries, economic efficiency, insufficient comprehensive research, terminological limitations, macroeconomic and political alignment, manufacturing enterprises.*

Introduction

The products manufactured in various regions, specifically the per capita gross domestic product (GDP), serve as an indicator of a country's overall economic performance when divided by its total population. We categorized countries into four groups based on their performance metrics and identified those with superior indicators within each group. Notably, Singapore emerged as a leader in the first group, followed by Austria in the second, Japan in the third, and Uzbekistan, distinguished by high performance, in the fourth group.

Despite the significant potential for regional development, Uzbekistan has not fully leveraged mechanisms widely used abroad, such as the establishment of special economic zones and attracting private capital to stimulate growth. These measures, along with the development of infrastructure projects (including roads, railways, information technology and communication systems, and specialized warehouses), are crucial for enhancing the competitiveness of the country's regions.

Research methodology

In the digital transformation of industrial enterprises within regions, it is essential to prioritize the security of their resources. Conducting risk assessments not only facilitates economic efficiency but also optimizes information security for industrial organizations. The development of a company's information environment, the implementation of new modules in corporate information systems, and the modernization of data transmission channels can lead to vulnerabilities and create a conducive environment for emerging information risks.

While existing literature addresses the overall security of national economies, states, specific regions, and industrial enterprises, there has been insufficient comprehensive research into the economic and information security issues related to entities operating within the regional industrial structure.

If we categorize regional industries economically, they primarily consist of the following natural resources:

1. General significance natural resources;
2. Material production resources;
3. Service sector resources.

Many contemporary economic theories, including concepts such as "post-industrial society," "information society," "knowledge economy," and "institutional structure of industry," as discussed by scholars like D. Bell, E. Toffler, and K. Drogobitskaya, are relevant to this discourse. However, certain terminological limitations may not always accurately reflect the essence of these perspectives.

In the Republic of Korea, the "Law on Comprehensive National Planning for Regional Development" has been enacted, leading to the establishment of specialized parks within various sectors, with a strong emphasis on infrastructure development. Programs have been developed to foster the growth of technoparks and technopolises. In developing countries, particularly Turkey, there is significant governmental support and incentives for regional development, with a particular focus on establishing growth points. Numerous regional programs and investment projects have been formulated and are currently being implemented in these countries.

Results and discussion

The development of integration processes in Europe has significantly enhanced the role of regional policy within the framework of the European Economic Community in recent years. A decade ago, regional policy was regarded merely as an additional avenue for achieving progress in strategic sectors of the EU's activities. By the late 1980s, it had gained considerable independent significance. With the implementation of the Maastricht Treaty, which established the European Union, the scope for executing EU regional policy expanded substantially, and the roles of specific regions within member states increased.

EU regional policy is guided by several key principles:

- **Strict Oversight of Resource Allocation:** Structural fund resources must be concentrated in the EU's least developed areas, with 80% of financial payments from this fund directed towards regions that lag in economic development.
- **Complementary Subsidies:** Structural subsidies are designed to be mutually reinforcing, meaning that EU institutions can only provide resources as supplementary to national programs and cannot independently designate intervention targets.

- **Macroeconomic and Political Coordination:** The EU aims for macroeconomic and political alignment among member states, ensuring that financial support for national regional development programs does not contradict the economic policies of these countries. Additionally, it is essential to monitor that funds from the EU budget are not misallocated due to a lack of consultation between national and local authorities.
- **Direct Cooperation among Member States:** Implementation of national regional programs should be based on direct collaboration among EU countries. This includes facilitating information exchange between relevant governments to ensure clarity in the objectives and methods of national program execution.

China's experience initially relied on the concept of "Allocating Productive Forces on an Equal Basis," which evolved into utilizing the "Relative Competitive Advantages of Regions." This approach prioritizes the development of competitive products and services, as well as tourism in regions with the highest potential. The establishment of special economic zones is complemented by the development of an "Open Areas" system, which also considers other central cities and districts within the country.

Global trends in regional policy exhibit several common characteristics, including:

- Decentralization
- Inter-regional Integration
- Environmental Protection
- Enhancement of Population Welfare, among others.

In many countries, the implementation of regional policy is supported by targeted programs, mechanisms for assisting border areas, and the establishment of special economic zones and clusters.

The implementation and development of digital transformation processes in regional industries are crucial for ensuring sustainability and relevance in the economic landscape. Promoting innovative growth within regional industrial enterprises serves as a significant driver of the national economic system. Consequently, digital transformation not only focuses on the digitization of regional industries but also aims to foster substantial innovative growth.

This transformation involves the automation and management of industrial systems, integrating organizational mechanisms that encompass automatic control systems, robotics, and computer-based management systems. Such frameworks enable the automatic oversight of industrial activities and processes. Enhancing the mechanisms of transformation processes within the production sector and the structural frameworks of the national economy is essential for achieving competitive advantages. In this context, political considerations, alongside technological advancement and economic growth, become imperative for ensuring the competitiveness and economic security of the national economy.

In implementing each economic mechanism, it is vital to develop state-supported initiatives tailored to specific sectors, which play a critical role in achieving macroeconomic balance and stability through regional policy execution. These disparities possess both objective and subjective characteristics. Objective characteristics include natural resources and regional inequalities in living conditions. Historically, each nation has evolved through the appropriation of its designated living space, influenced by the distribution of natural resources (such as mineral deposits, arable land, and water resources) and their varied geographical locations.

Conclusions

In enhancing the digital transformation processes within regional industries, theoretical and methodological research has yielded the following conclusions and recommendations aimed at effective organization within the regional economy. The development of stages in the transformation processes of regional industry is critically important. This enables the assessment and selection of innovative and investment projects aimed at achieving strategic industrial development goals at both the regional and national levels.

Additionally, it is vital to advance the theoretical and methodological aspects of regional industry and implement policies that effectively support these advancements. Establishing strong connections between financial institutions and manufacturing enterprises is essential to create a robust intellectual system that underpins sustainable economic growth and enhances the efficiency and continuity of regional industries.

In the context of regional development, it is crucial to diversify industrial structures within economic sectors and establish institutional processes that meet contemporary demands. Furthermore, scientific and theoretical approaches must be employed to execute key tasks in the stable development of the industry, ensuring the correct selection of objectives. The formulation of relevant decisions should also incorporate methodological approaches to innovative management within the regional industry.

An analysis of the scientific works of both international and domestic scholars on innovative industrial development has revealed a focus on the production aspects within various sectors of regional industries. This research has also examined the trends in the development of industries in foreign countries, including how these sectors are regulated by governmental policies. Recommendations have been made for adapting applicable practices from these foreign regions to Uzbekistan and its respective areas.

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